

A NEW PROCESS TO FABRICATE COATED FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY MATRIX COMPOSITE

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Introduction

The aim of the present study is to develop a protective coating on carbon fibers preventing the deleterious fiber-matrix interfacial reactions and retaining the structural integrity of fibers in matrix, without raising up the cost greatly. SiC was selected as a potential protective coating for C/Al system, whose properties are close to carbon and the reaction temperatures of SiC and matrix are above 700°C. By carefully controlling of coating process, a dense and homogeneous SiC layer can be formed on surface of fibers, which serves as barrier to fiber-matrix reactions. Furthermore, hybridizing SiC particles during Sol-gel process had been approached.

EXPERIMENTAL

SiC coatings are derived from Sol-gel route, in which carbon fibers are dragged through polycarbosilane solution, followed by several drying, dehydration and densification stage. In addition, SiC particles were added into polycarbosilane solution to incorporate hybridizing with Sol-gel process. Coated fibers were entwined into preforms, then vacuum pressure infiltrated by melting matrix alloy to get bulk materials. As-received fibers were also employed to give a control.

Three-point bending tests of composites reinforced with fibers of various treatment were conducted on Shimazu AG-10T testing machine to evaluate coating and hybridizing effect. Bending specimen were carefully polished to reduce surface defects' influence. Average of 10 specimen data is taken as the final result. Microstructure of coated fiber, as well as composites, were characterized by means of XRD, XPS, TEM and SEM. The fracture surface of bending specimen was checked by using SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bending strength and fracture feature of uncoated fibers, coated fibers and coating with hybridization fibers reinforced bulk composites were measured respectively, as shown in Table 1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Manufacturing of fiber reinforced composites in present study includes fiber coating, SiC particle hybridizing and vacuum pressure infiltration. Raw materials used are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Raw materials to manufacture C/Al composites

Item	Brand	Description
Carbon fiber	AS4C	E 260GPa, UTS 2300MPa
Matrix	A0 pure aluminum	E 30GPa UTS 65MPa
Polycarbosilane	commercial	average molecular weight 1500~2000
SiC particle	grade W5	average size 2~5 μ m

SiC coatings are derived from Sol-gel route, in which carbon fibers are dragged through polycarbosilane solution, followed by several drying, dehydration and densification stage. Fig.1 schematically shows the coating device. In addition, SiC particles were added into polycarbosilane solution to incorporate hybridizing with Sol-gel process.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of SiC Sol-gel coating

1. feeding reel; 2. Solution in ultrasonic tank(same position as hybridization); 3. low-temperature drying; 4. Mid-temperature drying and dehydration; 5. High-temperature dehydration and densification; 6. Take-up reel. The temperature of parts 3, 4 and 5 is 200°C, 550°C and 850°C~900°C, respectively. Argon is used as a protective atmosphere. The speed of fiber feeding is 0.1 m/min.

Coated fibers were enwinded into preforms, then vacuum pressure infiltrated by melting matrix alloy to get bulk materials. As-received fibers were also employed to give a control. Details of infiltration process could be found elsewhere[3].

Three-point bending tests of composites reinforced with fibers of various treatment were conducted on Shimazu AG-10T testing machine to evaluate coating and hybridizing effect. Bending specimen were carefully polished to reduce surface defects' influence. Average of 10 specimen data is taken as the final result.

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RESULTS

SEM observation had found that the surface of the coatings was smooth and homogeneous (Fig.2(a)), further study also found the distribution of hybridized SiC particles was even and the particles adhered to the SiC coatings well(Fig.2(b)).

(a) morphology of SiC coatings

(b) morphology of SiC coatings hybridized with SiC particles

Fig.2 SEM of SiC coatings

TEM showed a clear layer of SiC coating between fibers and the matrix, the thickness about $0.1\mu\text{m}$. (Fig.3)

The TEM work and quantitative XRD showed no apparent interfacial reaction between the coated fibers and the matrix, as shown in Fig.3. Compared to the clear interface of coated fibers reinforced aluminum composites, there were quite a lot reaction products between the uncoated carbon fibers and the matrix (Fig.4). The TEM diffraction pattern has identified the products as Al_4C_3 , which nucleated from the surface of carbon fiber and then grew into the matrix.

Fig.3. TEM of SiC coatings

Fig.4 Reaction products between uncoated fiber and matrix

The bending strength and fracture feature of bulk composites derived from uncoated fibers, coated fibers and coating with hybridization fibers were evaluated, respectively, as listed in Table 1.

Table 1. The bending strength of different fiber-treatment derived composites

Fiber treatment	Ratio to ROM value (%)	Fractography of fracture surface
as-received	21	brittle, too much reaction
Sol-gel SiC coating	48	mediate pull-out, reaction checked
Sol-gel SiC coating *(heat-treated)	48	mediate pull-out, reaction checked
Sol-gel coating, hybridized with SiC _p	70	pretty pull-out, reaction checked

*: the coated fibers have been heat-treated at 600°C for 6 hours.

DISCUSSION

During the Sol-gel process, the quality of SiC coatings is mainly controlled by solution concentration, treating temperatures and reeling speeds of the fibers. A high polycarbosilane: C₆H₁₄ ratios increase the productivity of SiC, but leading to a more brittle layer that will cause the fibers break during take-up reeling. The thermal stress is mostly caused during the contracting of the layers, leading to the cracks among the coatings. Through selecting proper process stages and temperature gradient, a smooth and uniform coating can be obtained.

The dense and homogeneous coatings can protect the fibers from reacting with the matrix. The uncoated fibers always become the nucleation sources, especially if there are some defects on the surface of the fibers[2]. With SiC coating, the reaction between carbon fibers and aluminum matrix is hindered. The SiC coatings functioned as a barrier layer with maintaining the physical strength.

In general, the tensile strength of the SiC coated carbon fibers is lower than that of the uncoated fibers which do not have a surface compressive stress, thus they are susceptible to surface damage during coating. But as a result of decreasing the Al₄C₃ by coatings, there were more pull-outs on the fracture surfaces which increased the strength significantly. The uncoated fibers reinforced composites showed a flat fracture surface, and the cracks broke through the fibers. The SiC coated fibers reinforced composites showed a rough fracture surface with many pull-outs, and the cracks expended along the boundaries of the fibers.

When put the coated fibers into ambient atmosphere at 600°C for 6 hours, there was no difference of the bend strength of bulk composites (Table. 1), showing the protective effects of the SiC coatings.

It was discovered that SiC_p hybridized coated C/Al composites had the highest ratio of strength to the ROM value. This is because the dispersed SiC particles can separate the fibers from adhering together which greatly deteriorate bulk materials' properties[4].

CONCLUSION

- 1) The described Sol-gel process is an effective fibers treatment with low secondary cost, which can combine fiber de-gluing, SiC coating and SiC particles hybridizing together.
- 2) The derived SiC coatings consist of crystallite and non-crystallite SiC. It is a dense and uniform layer with an average thickness about 0.1μm.
- 3) The SiC coatings can hinder the interface reaction, thus improve the properties of the composites.
- 4) The SiC_p hybridized coated C/Al composites get higher strength.

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